

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

STEROPES

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sampling strategy

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Satellite-based (Sentinel-2) soil sampling strategies for SOC
estimation at field- and farm-scale

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1 Introduction

The sense of urgency that emanated from the 2015 United Nations Climate Change Conference in Paris (COP 21) has spurred on the search for effective climate change mitigation measures in the past decade. Farming practices have received a lot of attention in this regard, because agricultural soils have seen a massive loss in their soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks ever since the onset of agriculture (Sanderman et al., 2017) and therefore possess a large potential for restoration (Lal et al., 2018; Minasny et al., 2017). Various farming practices could help with this restoration, (Batjes, 2019; Bossio et al., 2020; Paustian et al., 2016; Spencer et al., 2011) and this is driving an upsurge in new ‘carbon farming’ initiatives, both from the public and private sector, that aim to incentivize farmers to adopt these practices (Amelung et al., 2020; Black et al., 2020; Commission, 2021; Elkerbout et al., 2020; Guan et al., 2023). However, the lack of robust and cost-effective monitoring systems has proven a major barrier to the upscaling of these carbon farming initiatives (Commission, 2021; Oldfield et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2020). With the (currently still provisional) Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation, and relatedly the Soil Monitoring Law, the European Commission aims to tackle this issue and provide a statistically sound and cost-effective SOC monitoring or estimation framework (Commission, 2021; Günther et al., 2024; Kotschik et al., 2024).

Most existing SOC estimation methods make use of direct measurement through soil sampling and laboratory analyses (FAO, 2019; Smith et al., 2020). These methods require the development of a sampling strategy, which entails making decisions on sample size, sample pattern and sample locations (Brus & De Gruijter, 1997). It is possible to achieve very high accuracy with direct measurement, however, there are various complicating factors that can put a serious constraint on the cost-effectiveness of these estimation methods. All steps of direct measurement (i.e. sampling, processing and analysis) have an intrinsically high cost (Batjes et al., 2023; Smith et al., 2020). Furthermore, the large background carbon stocks, the large spatial variability (even at smaller operational management units, like field or farm scale) and the inherently slow carbon gains all make it more difficult to achieve the, often very high, desired accuracy with a limited budget, and thus sample size (Biswas & Zhang, 2018; Garten & Wullschleger, 1999; Goidts et al., 2009; Post et al., 2001; Smith et al., 2020; Vanguelova et al., 2016).

An alternative for direct measurement could be found with spectral methods that rely on the content-specific absorbance/reflectance of light on the soil surface in the visible and infrared (Vis-NIR: 400-1100 nm) and shortwave infrared (SWIR: 1100-2500 nm) regions of the electromagnetic spectrum (Ben-Dor et al., 2009; Chabrillat et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2020). These methods make use of prediction models, that are based on spectral libraries (comparison of traditional laboratory and reflectance measurements), to estimate the SOC content (Smith et al., 2020). Since these estimations don’t require any expensive and time-consuming

standard laboratory analyses once the spectral library is created, the spectral measurements are very useful for collecting high resolution information on SOC content and thus also for mapping at many different scales (Chabrilat et al., 2019). Larger scale estimation and mapping has been greatly facilitated by the diverse set of platforms, like UAVs or satellites, that have been equipped with spectral sensors in recent years (Bellon-Maurel & McBratney, 2011; England & Rossel, 2018; Nayak et al., 2019). Several studies have been able to use satellite-derived spectral data for SOC content estimation (Köchy et al., 2015; Poggio et al., 2021; Vaudour et al., 2022). However, these estimations are often still of relatively low accuracy, especially at smaller operational management scales (i.e. field or farm), and they are therefore seldom used for direct carbon monitoring in carbon farming initiatives (Andries et al., 2021). These low accuracy levels can be attributed to a broad set of potential disrupting factors, such as soil moisture content, texture, salinity, surface roughness, dry or green vegetation cover and weather conditions (e.g. cloud cover, sunshine variation) (Castaldi et al., 2023; Dvorakova et al., 2021; Tziolas et al., 2021; Vaudour et al., 2022).

Despite its relative inaccuracy as a direct estimation method, satellite-derived spectral data could still be a serious boon to SOC monitoring/estimation by providing a priori knowledge of the site-specific spatial variability for the development of optimized sampling strategies (Shao et al., 2021). Any sampling strategy that seeks to accurately estimate SOC content will need to take the entire range of SOC values within the zone of interest into account (Brus & Heuvelink, 2007). Sampling strategies that are based on the geographical space, like grid sampling, can offer a substantial improvement in cost-efficiency compared to simple random sampling and further improvements can be made by exploiting the relationship between SOC content and potential covariates (also referred to as ancillary data), which entails an optimization in the feature space (Brus & Heuvelink, 2007; Hengl et al., 2003; Minasny & McBratney, 2006). Multiple studies have used satellite-derived spectral data in this way as covariate, both at field (e.g. Guan et al., 2023; Potash et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2012; van der Voort et al., 2023) and farm-scale (e.g. Bettigole et al., 2023; Castaldi, Hueni, et al., 2019; de Gruijter et al., 2016; Deluz et al., 2020; Malone et al., 2018). However, the strong site-specific nature of the relationship between SOC content and covariates, like the soil's spectral patterns, still make it difficult to develop robust, scalable and easy to use methods for the optimization of sampling strategies (Bettigole et al., 2023; Kerry & Escola, 2021; Smith et al., 2020). Selection algorithms, like Kennard-Stone (e.g. Castaldi et al., 2019), Ospats (e.g. de Gruijter et al., 2016) and conditioned Latin hypercube sampling (e.g. van der Voort et al., 2023), have been successfully utilized to optimize sampling strategies for SOC content estimation based on satellite-derived spectral data. However, these algorithms do come with a certain requirement for computing power and programming skills. Many SOC monitoring initiatives therefore still rely on simpler random or regular grid sampling strategies (Bettigole et al., 2023; Smith et al., 2020).

This study is carried out within the framework of the STEROPES project of the European Joint H2020 Program SOIL (<https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/steropes/>). The overarching goal of this study is to develop cost-effective satellite-based sampling strategies for the determination of topsoil SOC content in cropland at field- and farm-scale. In Flanders (Belgium), the usefulness of a regional SOC map, that was recently developed by the Horizon 2020 project of ENVISION (see **Text box 1**), as source of ancillary data to optimize soil sampling at farm-scale will be investigated (map-based sampling strategy). However, since SOC maps are not publicly available for all regions of Europe, we will also look at the direct use of the Sentinel-2 spectral bands with the Kennard-Stone selection algorithm to help guide sampling strategies at field-scale in Italy (satellite-based sampling strategy). During the development of optimized sampling strategies, extra care will be taken to ensure that the new approaches are robust and easy to use. The complexity and need of extended computing power and programming skills of many existing optimized sampling strategies still forms a major barrier to their implementation by carbon monitoring initiatives (Bettigole et al., 2023; Smith et al., 2020). As a second step, we will compare the results from the newly developed farm-scale sampling strategies in Flanders with the estimates from the regional ENVISION SOC map to calibrate the ENVISION SOC map accordingly, to the site-specific farm-scale conditions (*ijken* – see for example Veris scan (van der Schans & van der Berg, 2013)). We will subsequently assess if the adapted ENVISION SOC map manages to estimate the topsoil SOC content for every field of the farm of interest at enhanced accuracy, while keeping the required sample size to a minimum. To be able to link the soil sampling results with the Sentinel-2 data, we decided to keep the smallest resolution pixels (10mx10m) of these satellites as sampling support (i.e. plot) for our newly developed sampling strategies.

The initial calibration sampling campaign for ENVISION took 16 subsamples in a Sentinel-2 pixel (i.e. plot) of 10mx10m, that were later bulked into one composite sample for lab analysis. This plot-scale sample size was calculated during the preparatory work for the [Flemish Cmon monitoring network](#) based on regional data on field-scale SOC variability (Letpens et al., 2021; Sleutel et al., 2021). Such an expanded sample size was deemed appropriate for the forest and grasslands soils that were included in the Cmon monitoring network, however, it seems highly likely that a smaller sample size could be used for just croplands with only limited impact on the precision of the SOC content estimation, while helping to reduce the overall costs.

Text box 1: ENVISION SOC map for Flanders

ENVISION is the acronym of the Horizon 2020 project “Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation” (2020-2024) that focuses on offering tools for the continuous, large scale and uninterrupted monitoring of farm management activities with regards to

sustainability (Tsardanidis et al., 2024). Five distinct business cases were developed within this project's framework that could use specific forms of earth observation data. Here our interest is limited to the business case developed by ILVO, on the monitoring of cropland topsoil SOC in Flanders by utilizing Sentinel-2 data. This source of satellite imagery from ESA ([Sentinel missions](#)) provides freely accessible, high-resolution data with both spatial and temporal variability. Sentinel-2 has a spatial resolution of 10 m for most bands and a revisit time of 5 days.

The methodology that was followed to get to the desired cropland SOC maps can be divided into five phases, as is depicted in *Figure 1*. In Phase One, the goal was to develop a cloudless collection of bare soil pixels. As a first step, it was required to distinguish between cropland and the other land-uses. This could be done either by way of the European Space Agency (ESA) WorldCover 10 m 2020 product, which provides a global land cover map for 2020 at 10 m resolution based on Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data, or with the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) information provided by the Flemish government. Besides that, disrupting factors, like cloud cover, soil moisture content and vegetation or plant residue cover, needed to be considered and were filtered out with a combination of thresholds on relevant spectral indices. Two, the modelling was performed in order to create a mapping between the extracted reflection signatures from the Bare Soil Collection and actual SOC measurements. Originally, the open-source, low-code machine learning library of [PyCaret](#) was used to perform data preparation, model training, hyperparameter tuning, analysis and interpretability, and model selection, but at a later stage (April 2024), this process was repeated with the [TensorFlow](#) machine learning platform. PyCaret tested a host of different machine learning algorithms in the PyCaret framework on Google Colab, to link Sentinel data from beginning 2018 to May 2022 and the Extra Trees Regression with standard options for PyCaret version 2 was chosen based on global statistics to generate the map, and some extra options such as sensitivity analysis, variable importance with Shapley values were integrated in the PyCaret network and applied. The TensorFlow approach was required to work in a new workflow which permitted API integration on the Google Cloud platform, and the TensorFlow map worked with more recent data from Sentinel-2, including data from 2022, 2023 until Januari 2024. The model itself was a basic ANN TensorFlow model. In the rest of the report the two distinct SOC maps will be referenced by their respective machine learning platform. The SOC measurements were carried out for 171 different sampling locations spread out over the different soil regions of Flanders (Tsardanidis et al., 2024). The selection of the exact sampling locations was carried out according to a stratified feature-based (i.e. 11 soil association regions based on the [Soil Association Map of Flanders](#)) approach with the [Kennard-Stone algorithm](#) (Kennard & Stone, 1969). The intent of this approach was to cover most SOC variability in croplands in Flanders. The sampling areas corresponded with

one Sentinel-2 pixel of 10mx10m dimensions, and the middle was determined with RTK GPS precision. As is presented in *Figure 2*, within this area 16 randomly selected subsamples were collected into one composite sample to deal with the small-scale spatial variability. In Phase Three, the deployed model was applied to all pixels belonging to the larger area of interest (i.e. all Flemish cropland). In Phase Four, a technical validation of the model was performed for each soil association region separately, to get a better understanding of the accuracy of the deployed models. *Figure 3* presents the results of the regional-scale validation for the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map. Phase Five consists of a broader evaluation and the making of improvements.

Significant Methodological Phases

Figure 1: Methodological phases followed in task 3.6 of the ENVISION project (Tsardanidis et al., 2024)

Figure 2: SOC sampling area, corresponding with one Sentinel-2 pixel (10mx10m). The orange X's depict the 16 randomly selected subsample locations.

Figure 3: Sensitivity analysis results per included region of the Soil Association Map of Flanders to evaluate the performance of the ENVISION PyCaret prediction model. The parameters assessed in this analysis were: the number of samples, Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), coefficient of determination (R2), Root Mean Squared Logarithmic Error (RMSLE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and Ratio of Performance to Deviation (RPD) (Tsardanidis et al., 2024).

The first-produced (using the PyCaret machine learning platform) SOC map for all croplands in Flanders is presented in Figure 4. In this map the SOC content varies between 0.9% and 1.9%, which is a distinctly shorter range than would be expected for Flemish croplands. The most recent results from the [Flemish Cmon monitoring network](#) show SOC content values for croplands (mean: 1.62%; standard deviation: 0.63%) that markedly exceed this range, especially in the upper ranges (Oorts et al., 2023). Similarly, the Bodemkundige Dienst van België has placed the target zone for sandy soils, common in the Belgian agricultural Zandstreek (Sand region) and the Kempen (Campines) (See Belgian soil map), between 1.8% and 2.8%, almost completely outside the current predicted range of the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map (Tits et al., 2024). The short range in SOC content within the ENVISION map can be largely explained by the small number of samples with more extreme SOC contents in the initial calibration dataset (n=171). The few extreme samples were additionally weighed down to limit their outlying impact on the overall prediction. The Extra Trees Regression model maybe also acquired part of the better scores on global statistics by a model prediction that defaults closer to the mean of dataset, which was less the case for the TensorFlow model, but is a general characteristic of most machine learning models.

The regional-scale accuracy (RMSE) of the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map varied between 0.03% and 0.33%, with most regions falling within the range of 0.03% to 0.11% and only the regions with dry sandy and loamy soils with humic and/or iron B horizons (#14) and with silty soils with texture B horizon and moderately dry

association (#32) showing less accurate validation results (Figure 3). The coefficient of determination (R^2) was substantially more variable, with values ranging between 0.00 and 0.63, so the prediction model doesn't have a really high goodness-of-fit (> 0.7) for any of the soil association regions. The RPD values make clear that the prediction model can be characterized as quite unreliable (< 1.4) for about half the soil association regions (# 14, 19, 29, 32 and 38) and only slightly fair (> 1.4 & < 2.0) for the other half (# 10, 15, 17, 27, 31 and 60) (Chang et al., 2001).

Figure 4: Original ENVISION PyCaret SOC map for all cropland in Flanders (Belgium). The main Belgian agricultural regions for Flanders are also indicated in Dutch.

Figure 5 presents the TensorFlow SOC map for all croplands in Flanders. This map has a considerably larger range in predicted topsoil SOC content (0.9-2.4%) than the first PyCaret map. It only became available during the later stages of the STEROPES project in April 2024.

2 Research questions

- Within this report we will focus on three broad research questions that are meant to guide us through important issues in the development of a statistically sound and cost-effective sampling strategy for SOC content determination of all the fields of a given farm. Research question 1 will be worked out in Section 3 of this report, while research questions 2 and 3 will both be worked out in Section 4. **Research question 1 (Section 3):** *Is it possible to reduce the plot-scale (10mx10m) subsampling costs by reducing the number of subsamples currently used in the protocol of the Flemish Cmon monitoring network and used for the original ENVISION sampling campaign (i.e. 16 subsamples), without drastically reducing the precision of the SOC content estimation?*
- **Research question 2 (Section 4):** *Can the Sentinel-2 spectral bands (satellite-based) or pre-existing SOC maps (map-based – here ENVISION PyCaret SOC map for the region of Flanders) provide us with adequate knowledge on topsoil SOC variability at field- and farm-scale to help optimize soil sampling strategies?*

- **Research question 3 (Section 4):** *Is it possible to meaningfully increase the accuracy of the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map at field-scale by its local (i.e. farm-scale) calibration?*

3 Determination of a cost-effective plot-scale sample size (D7.3)

Research question 1: *Is it possible to reduce the plot-scale (10mx10m) subsampling costs by reducing the number of subsamples currently used in the protocol of the Flemish Cmon monitoring network and used for the original ENVISION sampling campaign (i.e. 16 subsamples), without drastically reducing the precision of the SOC content estimation?*

3.1 Precision

As a first step, we conducted a literature review for data on spatial variability of SOC content. The criteria for the literature research were the following: 1) climatic conditions similar to Flanders (Belgium), so mainly northern Europe and America, 2) assessment of smaller spatial scales, which would include small plots up to entire fields, and 3) determination of SOC content by standard laboratory analyses. The main focus was on cropland soils, but some studies on grassland and forest soils were also included as useful comparisons, since these land-uses were also taken into account for the original determination of an appropriate plot-scale sample size (16) for the Flemish Cmon monitoring network (Letkens et al., 2021; Sleutel et al., 2021) and the original Flanders-wide sampling campaign for the ENVISION SOC map. Because of the link with remote sensing, our primary focus was on the surface layer (0-10 cm), however, studies that looked at larger sampling depths were also included in the review, as long as the surface layer was included.

Table 1 summarizes the scientific literature found during this review. We have found 33 relevant studies that looked at cropland, six that looked at grassland and five at forest soils. Some studies are included several times because they present data on various relevant soil types (D'Haene, 2008; Schruppf et al., 2011), spatial scales (Goidts et al., 2009; Saby et al., 2008) or depth intervals (D'Haene, 2008). The coefficient of variability ($=s/\bar{x}$; CV) for cropland soils varied between 3.5% and 51.7%. However, the outlying high values were almost all found for relatively large fields, which are far more common in North America and Australia than in northern Europe (e.g. average field size in Belgium in 2022 was 1.1 ha) (e.g. Cambardella et al., 1994; Lafrance & Banton, 1995; Mulla, 1993; Nolin et al., 1996; Robertson et al., 1993; Singh et al., 2012), and are thus less

comparable to the plot-scale (100 m²) in our experimental design. Most of the more relevant studies found a CV that was below 10%. For grasslands the CV varied between 8% and 17.4%. For forest soils the CV varied between 10% and 50%. The higher spatial variability of SOC content for grasslands and forests compared to croplands has been widely observed (e.g. Conant et al., 2003; Goidts et al., 2009; Poeplau et al., 2022; Stanley et al., 2023). The most important reasons for these differences can be attributed to the homogenizing effect of tillage operations in croplands, the patchiness of grazing and manure deposition on grasslands and the scattered presence of vegetation in forests (De Vos, 2009; Goidts et al., 2009; Poeplau et al., 2022; Stanley et al., 2023). The markedly lower spatial variability of SOC content in cropland, compared to grassland and forests, means that a lower sample size will be required to achieve comparable levels of precision (Conant et al., 2003; Smith, 2004; Vanguelova et al., 2016).

Table 1: Overview of existing scientific literature on smaller (i.e. plot – field) scale spatial variability (represented by the coefficient of variability - %) of SOC content in Northern European and American cropland, grassland and forest topsoils.

#	Reference	Land-use	Country	Soil type	Plot size (m ²)	Depth (cm)	Plot sample size	Coefficient of variation (CV - %)
1	Boekhold & Van Der Zee (1992)	Cropland	The Netherlands	Sandy	Field (0.5 ha)	0-20	166	11.0
2	Mulla (1993)	Cropland	USA (Washington)	Ultic Haploxeroll	Field (8 ha)	0-30	172	42.0
3	Robertson et al. (1993)	Cropland	USA (Michigan)	Loam	Field (2.2 ha)	0-20	251	51.7
4	Cahn et al. (1994)	Cropland	USA (Illinois)	Mollisol	2 500	0-15	200	18.0
5	Cambardella et al. (1994)	Cropland	USA (Iowa)	Silty clay loam	Field (6.25-10 ha)	0-15	72-241	22.0-31.0
6	Lafrance & Banton (1995)	Cropland	Canada	Sand	Field (1.5 ha)	5-15	110	30.0
7	Nolin et al. (1996)	Cropland	Canada	Aquepts	Field (10 ha)	0-15	130	25.0
8	Röver & Kaiser (1999)	Cropland	Germany	Loamy silt	3 800	0-15	81	5.0-6.7
9	Manies et al. (2001)	Cropland	USA (Iowa)	Typic Hapludolls	Field	0-20	3	14.6
10	Kätterer et al. (2004)	Cropland	Sweden	-	Field	0-25	4-32	1.0-27.0
11	Shukla et al. (2004)	Cropland	Austria	Loam-Sandy loam	Field (6.25 ha)	0-15	60	14.0
12	Kravchenko et al. (2006)	Cropland	USA (Michigan)	Loam	3600	0-5	20	11.0-28.0
13	Oorts (2006)	Cropland	France	Silt	Field	0-20	-	8.0
14	Montagne et al. (2007)	Cropland	France	Albeluvisol	400	0-30	16	7.5
15	D'Haene (2008)	Cropland	Belgium (Flanders)	Sandy loam	Field	0-5	5	8.7
16	D'Haene (2008)	Cropland	Belgium (Flanders)	Sandy loam	Field	5-10	5	5.8

17	<i>D'Haene (2008)</i>	Cropland	Belgium (Flanders)	Silt	Field	0-5	5	4.0
18	<i>D'Haene (2008)</i>	Cropland	Belgium (Flanders)	Silt	Field	5-10	5	3.3
19	<i>Patzold et al. (2008)</i>	Cropland	Germany	Silt	Field	0-30	30	8.4
20	<i>Saby et al. (2008)</i>	Cropland	Europe	Broad range	1-400	0-30	-	3.5
21	<i>Saby et al. (2008)</i>	Cropland	Europe	Broad range	400-10 000	0-30	-	5.8
22	<i>Saby et al. (2008)</i>	Cropland	Europe	Broad range	10 000-200 000	0-30	-	8.0
23	<i>Sleutel et al. (2008)</i>	Cropland	Belgium (Flanders)	Light sandy loam	Field	0-30	15	9.4
24	<i>Goidts et al. (2009)</i>	Cropland	Belgium (Wallonia)	Loam	50.3	0-30	5	8.0
25	<i>Goidts et al. (2009)</i>	Cropland	Belgium (Wallonia)	Loam	Field	0-30	23-47	8.0
26	<i>Moeskops (2010)</i>	Cropland	Belgium	Sandy loam	Field	0-20	-	2.8-9.9
27	<i>Kumhálová et al. (2011)</i>	Cropland	Czech Republic	Haplic Luvisol	Field (11.5 ha)	-	70	9.5-11.7
28	<i>Piotrowska et al. (2011)</i>	Cropland	Poland	Eutric Cambisols	Field (50 ha)	0-10	50	28.5
29	<i>Schrumpf et al. (2011)</i>	Cropland	Germany	Phaeozem	Field	0-30	100	5.0
30	<i>Schrumpf et al. (2011)</i>	Cropland	France	Cambisol	Field	0-30	100	10.0
31	<i>Singh et al. (2012)</i>	Cropland	Australia	Sand	Field (68 ha)	0-10	90	30.8
32	<i>Lettens et al. (2021)</i>	Cropland	Belgium (Flanders)	Broad range	Field (1-2 ha)	0-10	20	7.0
33	<i>Poeplau et al. (2022)</i>	Cropland	Germany	Broad range	400	0-30	16	8.0
34	<i>Goidts et al. (2009)</i>	Grassland	Belgium (Wallonia)	Loam	50.26	0-30	23-47	15.0
35	<i>Schrumpf et al. (2011)</i>	Grassland	France	Andosol	Field	0-30	100	8.0
36	<i>Schrumpf et al. (2011)</i>	Grassland	UK	Cambisol	Field	0-30	100	11.0
37	<i>Sleutel et al. (2011)</i>	Grassland	Belgium (Flanders)	Loamy sand	Field	0-10	-	17.4
38	<i>Lettens et al. (2021)</i>	Grassland	Belgium (Flanders)	Broad range	Field (1-2 ha)	0-10	20	12.0
39	<i>Poeplau et al. (2022)</i>	Grassland	Germany	Broad range	400	0-30	16	12.0
40	<i>Conant et al. (2003)</i>	Forest	USA	Broad range	10	0-30	12	10.0-50.0
41	<i>Schöning et al. (2006)</i>	Forest	Germany (Thüringen)	Silt	Field (1 ha)	0-12	45	30.0
42	<i>Montagne et al. (2007)</i>	Forest	France	Albeluvisol	400	0-30	16	16.0-28.0
43	<i>De Vos (2009)</i>	Forest	Belgium (Flanders)	Broad range	Field (1.6-6.9 ha)	0-15	50	36.0
44	<i>Lettens et al. (2021)</i>	Forest	Belgium (Flanders)	Broad range	Field (1-2 ha)	0-10	48	30.0

Figure 6 presents the precision that could be achieved for the plots and fields presented in *Table 1* by varying the sample size. Precision is here represented by the (95%) margin of error (MOE) which equals half the length of the 95 % confidence interval. A 95% confidence interval around the sample mean is as follows (van Belle, 2008):

$$\bar{Y} \pm 2 s/\sqrt{n} = \bar{Y} \pm MOE$$

with \bar{Y} the mean SOC content, $2 \sim 1.96$ the 97.5 % percentile of a normal distribution and n is the sample size.

So, if we require that $MOE \leq \Delta$, then the corresponding sample size should be:

$$n \geq 4 \frac{s^2}{\Delta^2}$$

This relationship makes clear that the sample size increases fast if a small MOE is aimed for. Aiming for a MOE half as small implies that the sample size should be four times as large.

The values of the mean SOC content were gathered from the preliminary (2021-2022: first work year) results for the Flemish Cmon monitoring network (Oorts et al., 2023). For the 0-10 cm layer of cropland soils a mean SOC content of 1.62% ($n=55$) was found, for permanent grassland this was 3.81% ($n=46$) and for forests 5.17% ($n=51$). Despite its incompleteness (total sample size every 10 years: $n_{\text{cropland}} = 794$; $n_{\text{permanent grassland}} = 406$; $n_{\text{forests}} = 490$), the ongoing Cmon monitoring network provides us with the most recent and comprehensive (good geographical spread) available for Flanders.

The results presented in *Figure 6* highlight the importance of a large sample size to achieve acceptable levels of precision, even for relatively small spatial scales, in forests and to a lesser extent also in grasslands. In cropland, on the other hand, smaller sample size seems to be acceptable.

Figure 6: Relation between the margin of error for the topsoil SOC content (%) and the sample size for cropland (yellow), grassland (green) and forest (red) at plot- up to field-scale. The full lines indicate the minimum and maximum variability found for each land-use. The measures of plot-scale variability (coefficient of variance – CV) were collected from existing scientific literature (see Table 1). The values of mean 0-10 cm layer SOC content (i.e. cropland: 1.62%; grassland: 3.81%; 5.17%) were gathered from the preliminary results of the Cmon monitoring network in Flanders (Oorts et al., 2023).

From all studies listed in Table 1, the spatial scales investigated by Montagne et al. (2007) (400 m² – #14), Saby et al. (2008) (1-400 m² – #20), Goidts et al. (2009) (50.3 m² – #24) and Poeplau et al. (2022) (400 m² – #33) came closest to the experimental conditions of our study (100 m²). The studies of Montagne et al. (2007) and Goidts et al. (2009) were thought less useful for our situation, because they had focused on a narrow range of soil types, while Saby et al. (2008) and Poeplau et al. (2022) assessed a broad range of European soils. Eventually, the value of spatial variability from Poeplau et al. (2022) was selected for our own calculations of expected precision, because it offered the most conservative estimation (8%). Figure 7 presents the expected precision with varying sample size for this level of spatial variability. At 16 the margin of error is found at 0.06%, only slightly above the detection limit of 0.04% at the laboratory of ILVO, and it stays below 0.10% until a sample size of seven. In Figure 8 the percentual change in the margin of error is given for each change in sample size by one. With the change in sample size from seven to eight there still is a considerable improvement to be obtained in terms of precision, but after that the gain starts to level off. At a sample size of eight, we could expect a margin of error of 0.09% (Figure 7), which would mean a 29% reduction from the sample size of 16.

Figure 7: Variation in the margin of error for the topsoil SOC content (%) with the sample size expected for cropland at plot scale (i.e. 100 m²) by Poeplau et al. (2022) (CV: 8.0%).

Figure 8: Change (%) in the margin of error by a stepwise (one) increase in sample size.

3.2 Comparison of data on plot-scale precision from scientific literature to experimental Flemish conditions

3.2.1 Experiment

To scrutinize the results for precision of SOC content determination that were presented in Section 3.1, we decided to replicate the sampling of three distinct plots of the experimental sampling campaign discussed in Section **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** three times each. This replication of the composite samples (8 subsamples) allowed us to estimate a CV value (and derived margin of error value) that could be compared with the results from scientific literature presented in *Table 1*.

One replicated sampling plot was selected randomly for each of the three soil types from the Belgian soil classification (i.e. silt (A – *Leem*), sandy loam (L – *Zandleem*) and light sandy loam (P – *Licht zandleem*) – (Van Ranst & Sys, 2000)) that were found on the two experimental farms (One in the Belgian municipality of Asse and the other in the municipality of Meise) that are characterized in more detail in Section 4.1.1.2. The three selected plots were:

- Asse – sampling plot 19 (silt)
- Meise – sampling plot 6 (sandy loam)
- Meise – sampling plot 11 (light sandy loam)

The exact locations of these replicated sampling plots are presented in *Figure 9*.

Figure 9: Locations of the three replicated sampling plots (see numbers) in the farms in Asse (blue) and Meise (red). The soil types found within the boundaries of the indicated cropland fields are: dry silt (red), moist silt (dark red), wet silt (orange), dry sandy loam (yellow), moist sandy loam (light green), wet sandy loam (dark green) and moist light sandy loam (blue).

3.2.2 Results

Results of the replicated SOC content determination of the topsoil (0-10 cm) of the selected sampling plots are presented in *Table 2*. The measured SOC content varied between 1.16% at sampling plot 11 and 1.99% at sampling plot 6 both from the farm in Meise. The plot-scale variation (CV) ranged between 1.2% at sampling plot 6 of the farm in Meise and 7.1% at the sampling plot 19 of the farm in Asse. These CV values all fall within the range observed in *Table 1*, although rather at the lower section of this range. In Section 3.1, we reasoned that a CV value of 8.0%, as found by Poeplau et al. (2022), would be a prudent choice to use when calculating the desired plot-scale sample size. Since none of the CV values of the replicated sampling plots were found to be higher than 8.0%, we can safely assume that we will not have overestimated the expected precision of the SOC content determination. In fact, with the average CV of 4.3% derived at the farms, we would expect a precision (margin of error) of 0.045% at a sample size of eight (*Figure 10*), so 50% better than expected by Poeplau et al. (2022) (*Figure 8*).

Table 2: Replicated ($n=3$) SOC content (%) of 0-10 cm depth interval at three experimental plots on distinct soil texture

Farm	Sample nr.	Soil texture	SOC content (%) – Replications			Average (%)	Standard deviation (%)	CV (%)
			A	B	C			
Asse	HVP_19	Silt	1.49	1.26	1.33	1.36	0.10	7.1
Meise	DL_6	Sandy loam	1.99	1.93	1.96	1.96	0.02	1.2
Meise	DL_11	Light sandy loam	1.17	1.28	1.16	1.20	0.05	4.5
Average:								4.3

Figure 10: Variation in the margin of error for the 0-10 cm SOC content (%) with the sample size expected for the experimental conditions at plot-scale (i.e. 100 m²) with a CV of 4.3%.

3.2.3 Costs (ILVO test case – Flanders)

Sampling campaigns for the determination of SOC content by laboratory analyses are generally associated with relatively high costs (Batjes et al., 2023; Viscarra Rossel & Brus, 2018). The most important sources of cost for farm-scale sampling campaigns are sampling labor by field technicians, laboratory processing and analysis and fuel for transport. Some more detailed information on the contemporary (February 2024) costs associated with these factors at ILVO in Flanders (Belgium) is presented in *Table 3*. The cost of the sampling equipment, like RTK GPS and augur set, was not included in this calculation, since we can assume that most of the equipment can be used for multiple years. This is how the products are marketed. The cost for sample preparation and laboratory analysis does take personnel, overhead and machine/consumables into account.

Table 3: Contemporary (Q1 2024) information on the costs associated with SOC sampling campaigns at the research institute of ILVO in Flanders (Belgium)

Source	Costs
Personnel (2 Field technicians)	2 x € 366 workday ⁻¹
Sample preparation and laboratory analysis (dry combustion) – Research laboratory; no market prices	€ 41.30 sample ⁻¹
Fuel (diesel)	€ 1.867 l ⁻¹

A change in the plot-scale sample size (number of subsamples for one composite sample) is expected to have a large influence on the costs associated with personnel for sampling and potentially also on the costs associated with fuel consumption. However, the latter factor will mainly be impacted if the change in sample size alters the duration of the sampling campaign to such a degree that extra or less days are required. A change in sample size will not impact the costs associated with laboratory analysis, since it will not alter the total number of samples to be analyzed in a sampling campaign.

In *Table 4* we present the costs associated with the experimental sampling campaign at the farm in Asse, Flanders (see Section 4.1.1.2). In total 64 composite samples were taken on the farm's 71.4 ha of cropland. All fields are geographically concentrated, the maximum distance between two fields is 2.8 km. The travel time between ILVO and the farm is around 30 minutes by car. The overall costs were calculated for both a plot-scale sample size of 16 and eight. We estimated that the sampling of one plot with 16 subsamples would take around 30 minutes (i.e. 10 minutes to locate sampling location with RTK GPS and 20 minutes for the actual sampling), while this could be reduced to 20 minutes (i.e. 10 minutes to locate sampling location with RTK GPS and 10 minutes for the actual sampling) when only eight subsamples were taken. The traveling time between sampling locations was kept constant at 15 minutes. According to these estimations, the sampling size of 16 would allow for 8.7 plots to be sampled by two field technicians per workday (= 7.5 h) and would therefore require 7.4 workdays to sample all 64 plots. The sampling size of eight would allow for 11.1 plots to be sampled per workday and require just 5.7 workdays to complete the sampling campaign. As a result, the sample size of 16 would cost € 5673.2, while the sample size of eight would cost € 4822.7. Consequently, a 15% reduction in overall costs could be achieved by halving the plot-scale sampling size from 16 to eight for this test case situation.

Table 4: Costs associated with sampling 44 Sentinel-2 plots/pixels for topsoil SOC content determination with 16 and 8 subsamples at farm in Asse, Flanders

Source of cost	16 subsamples	8 subsamples
Personnel	€ 5405.5	€ 4204.3
Sample preparation and laboratory analysis	€ 2643.2	€ 2643.2
Fuel	€ 219.3	€ 170.6
Total	€ 8268.0	€ 7018.1

Research question 1: *Is it possible to reduce the plot-scale (10mx10m) subsampling costs by reducing the number of subsamples currently used in the protocol of the Flemish Cmon monitoring network and used*

for the original ENVISION sampling campaign (i.e. 16 subsamples), without drastically reducing the precision of the SOC content estimation?

Based on scientific literature, the change in the plot-scale (10m x 10m) sample size from 16 to eight for the determination of cropland topsoil SOC content in Flanders was expected to worsen the precision (95% margin of error) by 30% from 0.06% to 0.09%, while reducing the overall costs in our experimental test case by 15%. The results derived from three replicated experimental sampling plots (0.045%) indicated that the values derived from scientific literature were not overestimating, but rather underestimating the precision of plot-scale topsoil SOC content determination at Flemish cropland conditions. Within our experimental conditions, we thought that this expected slight loss in precision would be an acceptable trade-off for the given reduction in sampling costs. However, this decision is very case dependent (e.g. increase in budget, precision/accuracy becomes limiting factor) and could relatively easily be reconsidered under new conditions or objectives with the results provided in this section.

4 Satellite-based sampling strategies (D7.1)

Research question 2 (Section 4): *Can the Sentinel-2 spectral bands (satellite-based) or pre-existing SOC maps (map-based – e.g. ENVISION PyCaret SOC map for the region of Flanders) provide us with adequate knowledge on topsoil SOC variability at field- and farm-scale to help optimize soil sampling strategies?*

Research question 3 (Section 4): *Is it possible to meaningfully increase the accuracy of the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map at field-scale by its local (i.e. farm-scale) calibration?*

4.1 Materials and Methods

4.1.1 Test sites

The newly developed satellite-based sampling strategies were assessed at three test sites: one in the province of Parma in Italy and two in the province of Vlaams-Brabant (Flanders, Belgium) in the municipalities of Asse and Meise (*Figure 11*). The Italian test site consists of two adjacent cropland fields on which a new sampling strategy, that was directly based on the Sentinel-2 spectral bands with the Kennard-Stone selection algorithm (satellite-based), was compared to a simple random sampling strategy. At the Belgian test site in Asse, the satellite-based sampling strategy was tested at farm-scale and compared to a sampling strategy based on a pre-existing SOC map (see **Text box 1**) for the region of Flanders (map-based). At the Belgian test site in Meise, the map-based sampling strategy was tested at farm-scale. We explicitly searched for one spatially concentrated farm with relatively homogeneous soil types (Asse) and another more spatially extended with a broader range of soil types (Meise). The sampling strategies will be discussed in more detail in Section 4.1.3.

Figure 11: Location of the test sites in Parma, Italy (field-scale) and Asse and Meise, Flanders – Belgium (Farm-scale)

4.1.1.1 Italian test site

The Italian test site (*Figure 12*) consist of two fields (8 ha), located in the Po Valley North Italy, in a completely flat croplands area. The two fields are situated in the area adjacent to the main Barilla spa plant in the province of Parma. This area consists of well drained and deep alluvial soils classified as Fluvi-Eutric Cambisols (WRB, 2015); the surface soil layers are calcareous with clay loam texture; the deeper layers are more calcareous with loam texture. Fields were managed by crop rotation alternating cereals and leguminous; fields are crossed by drainage channels running parallels 30 m from each other. Tillage is usually carried out

with a subsoiler (30 – 40 cm) or with a disk harrow (20 -30 cm). Mineral fertilization is normally applied, but 30 t ha⁻¹ of compost was added in 2022.

Figure 12: Italian test site (field-scale – blue field boundaries) in Parma

4.1.1.2 Belgian test sites

The study area of the Belgian test sites has a temperate maritime climate with mild winters and warm summers (Kottek et al., 2006) with an average yearly temperature of 11.0°C and average yearly rainfall of 829.7 mm (KMI long-term average climate data – 1991-2020 – for municipalities of Asse and Meise).

Asse

The first farm has a total cropland area of 71.4 ha, divided into 19 fields that are all located in the municipality of Asse. As is indicated in *Figure 13*, the fields were given a reference number between 1 and 19, to differentiate in further reporting. The cropland of this farm is spatially concentrated. The furthest distance between two fields (i.e. between 10 and 13) is 2.6 km.

Figure 13: Locations of the 19 cropland fields of the farm in the municipality of Asse in Flanders, Belgium.

Table 5 provides a short summary of the experimental fields. The size of the fields varies between 0.39 ha (field 19) and 18.3 ha (field 1), with an average field size of 3,6 ha. The standard crop rotation on this farm includes winter wheat, sugar beet, potatoes, brussels sprouts and maize. However, some fields (i.e. 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13 and 19) are mostly kept out of this crop rotation and are cultivated by a neighboring dairy farmer for fodder production with a sequence of English ryegrass as winter crop (1 cut in spring) and maize. The latter group of fields are relatively small, wet or jagged in shape. The soil cover at the time of the experimental sampling campaign (February and March 2024) varied between bare (fields 1 and 16), covered with (cover) crop residue (fields 2, 3, 12, 14, 15, 18 and 19) and green vegetation (fields 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13 and 17).

Table 5 also presents the soil texture and drainage classes that are expected for the experimental fields according to the Belgian soil map (Figure 14– Van Ranst & Sys, 2000). Almost all the fields are classified as homogeneous silty soils. Only field 2 has a small spot of sandy loam soil. The drainage classes varied more broadly: from “dry” over “moist” to “wet”. The “wet” area was restricted to small areas at the parcel boundaries of fields 1, 6 and 9. Fields 2, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11 and 19 are characterized as homogeneously “dry”, while only field 4 can be characterized as completely “moist”. Most remaining fields contain a mixture of “dry” and “moist” areas, except for fields 1 and 9, which are a mixture of “dry”, “moist” and “wet” areas, and field 9, which is a mixture of “moist” and “wet”. According to the WRB classification system the soils of the farm

in Asse are mostly Cutanic Luvisols, with smaller areas of Stagnic Cutanic and Endogleyic Luvisols (Dondeyne et al., 2014; WRB, 2015). On the Soil Association Map of Flanders, that was used for the stratified selection of the sampling locations for the initial ENVISION calibration dataset (see **Text box 1**), all the fields of this farm fall within region nr. 32, characterized by silty soils with texture B horizon and moderately dry association.

Table 5: Characteristics of the 19 cropland fields of farm in Asse: area, soil cover at the time of soil sampling, primary crop(s) for the 2023 & 2024 growing seasons (excluding cover crops) and soil texture and drainage classes derived from the Belgian soil classification map.

Field nr.	Area (ha)	Soil cover	Crop 2023	Crop 2024	Texture class	Drainage class	Soil Association nr.
1	18.3	Bare	Potatoes	Maize	Silt	Dry, moist & wet	32
2	7.2	Brussels sprouts residue	Brussels sprouts	Maize	Silt & sandy loam	Dry	32
3	2.9	Brussels sprouts residue	Brussels sprouts	Maize	Silt	Dry & wet	32
4	1.1	English ryegrass	English ryegrass – Maize	English ryegrass – Maize	Silt	Moist	32
5	4.6	Winter wheat	Sugar beet	Winter wheat	Silt	Dry	32
6	2.0	English ryegrass	English ryegrass – Maize	English ryegrass – Maize	Silt	Moist & wet	32
7	0.4	English ryegrass	English ryegrass – Maize	English ryegrass – Maize	Silt	Dry	32
8	0.7	English ryegrass	English ryegrass – Maize	English ryegrass – Maize	Silt	Dry	32
9	0.9	English ryegrass	English ryegrass – Maize	English ryegrass – Maize	Silt	Dry, moist & wet	32
10	1.8	English ryegrass	English ryegrass – Maize	English ryegrass – Maize	Silt	Dry	32
11	3.9	Winter wheat	Sugar beet	Winter wheat	Silt	Dry	32
12	2.1	Maize stubble	Maize	Maize	Silt	Dry & moist	32
13	1.0	English ryegrass	English ryegrass – Maize	English ryegrass – Maize	Silt	Dry & moist	32
14	4.6	Japanese oat – phacelia residue	Winter wheat	Brussels sprouts	Silt	Dry & moist	32
15	5.5	Japanese oat – phacelia residue	Winter wheat	Brussels sprouts	Silt	Dry & moist	32
16	2.4	Bare	Sugar beet	Maize	Silt	Dry & moist	32
17	3.7	English ryegrass	English ryegrass – Maize	English ryegrass – Maize	Silt	Dry & moist	32
18	8.0	Maize stubble	Maize	Potatoes	Silt	Dry & moist	32
19	0.4	Maize stubble	Maize	Maize	Silt	Dry	32
Total:	71.4						

Figure 14: Soil types (texture and drainage classes of Belgian soil classification) present in the immediate vicinity of the farm in Asse. The soil types found within the boundaries of the indicated cropland fields are: dry silt (light red), moist silt (medium red), wet silt (dark red) and dry sandy loam (yellow-green).

Meise

The second farm has a total cropland area of 16.3 ha, divided into nine fields. *Figure 15* presents the location of these cropland fields and indicates the corresponding reference numbers. Fields 1, 2 and 5 are found in the municipality of Meise, fields 3, 4 and 6 in Grimbergen and fields 7, 8 and 9 in Willebroek. The distance between fields 3 and 9 is 11.9 km.

Figure 15: Locations of the nine cropland fields of the farm in the municipalities of Grimbergen, Meise and Willebroek in Flanders, Belgium.

Table 6 gives a short summary of the nine experimental fields. The size of the fields varies between 0.4 ha (field 1) and 4.1 ha (field 2), with an average field size of 1.8 ha. Four fields (1, 3, 4 and 7) are smaller than 1 ha. The crop rotation includes maize, potatoes and winter wheat (or winter barley). The soil cover at the time of the experimental sampling campaign (February 2024) was either bare (field 5), covered with maize stubble (3, 4, 6, 7, 8 and 9) or green vegetation (fields 1 and 2).

Table 6 also presents the soil texture and drainage classes that are expected for the experimental fields according to the Belgian soil map (

Figure 16 – Van Ranst & Sys, 2000)). In contrast to farm in Asse, which is characterized by homogeneous silt soils (Figure 14), the farm in Meise is spread out over three distinct soil types according to the Belgian soil

map (

Figure 16): fields 3 and 4 are classified as silt, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 as sandy loam and 7 as light sandy loam. Also, in terms of drainage class the fields can be considered quite varied: “dry” for fields 3, 4 and 6, “moist” for fields 1, 2, 7, 8 and 9 and “wet” for field 5. On the Soil Association Map of Flanders fields 1, 2 and 5 fall within region nr. 29 (wet sandy loam soils with texture B horizon or with crumbled texture B horizon), fields 3 and 4 in region nr. 31 (silty soils with texture B horizon: normal association), field 6 in region nr. 28 (dry sandy loam soils with texture B horizon or with crumbled texture B horizon) and fields 7, 8 and 9 in region nr. 19 (complex of associations 15 “wet sandy and loamy sand soils with humic and/or iron B horizon” and 17 “wet sandy to light sandy loam soils with color B horizon or with texture B horizon”).

Table 6: Characteristics of the 9 cropland fields of the farm in Meise: area, soil cover at the time of soil sampling, primary crop(s) for the 2023 & 2024 growing seasons (excluding cover crops) and soil texture and drainage classes derived from the Belgian soil classification map.

Field nr.	Area (ha)	Soil cover	Crop 2023	Crop 2024	Texture class	Drainage class	Soil Association nr.
1	0.4	English ryegrass	English ryegrass	English ryegrass	Sandy loam	Moist	29
2	4.1	Winter barley	Winter wheat	Winter barley	Sandy loam	Moist & wet	29

3	0.8	Maize stubble	Maize	Potatoes	Silt	Dry	31
4	0.9	Maize stubble	Maize	Potatoes	Silt	Dry	31
5	2.3	Bare	Potatoes	Winter wheat	Sandy loam	Moist & wet	29
6	2.4	Maize stubble	Maize	Potatoes	Sandy loam	Dry & moist	28
7	1.0	Maize stubble	Maize	Maize	Light sandy loam	Moist	19
8	3.0	Maize stubble	Maize	Maize	Sandy loam	Moist	19
9	1.4	Maize stubble	Maize	Maize	Sandy loam	Moist	19
Total:	16.3						

Figure 16: Soil types (texture and drainage classes of Belgian soil classification) present in the immediate vicinity of the farm in Meise. The soil types found within the boundaries of the indicated cropland fields are: dry silt (red), dry sandy loam (yellow), moist sandy loam (green) and wet sandy loam (dark green).

4.1.2 Sentinel-2 composite layer – Mosaicking

A pixelwise temporal mosaicking approach was applied for the selection of bare soil images using Sentinel-2 imagery collections and obtaining composite bare soil layers for each test site from the time series 2020 – 2022 (Castaldi et al., 2023). The mosaicking approach was implemented by using the *rgee* R package (Aybar et al., 2020) to wrap the Earth Engine Python API for working on the Google Earth Engine environment (Gorelick et al., 2017) from within R (R Core Team, 2024). Google Earth Engine is a cloud-based platform

which was here used to gain access to Copernicus Sentinel-2 Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) level 2A dataset provided by European Space Agency (ESA).

The approach consisted of two steps. In the first step, three filters were applied for each pixel and acquisition date to identify and select bare soil pixels:

- I. **Atmospheric filter.** This includes a cloud filter to remove dates affected by clouds and cloud shadow. The cs quality band from the combination between Cloud Score+ and S2_HARMONIZED dataset was used with a cs threshold of 0.7 to remove thin clouds, haze, and cirrus shadows. The cs value is the similarity between the observed pixel and theoretical clear reference pixel based on their spectral distance. A snow mask was also applied using the MSK_SNOWPRB quality band provided by ESA, removing records with >10% probability of snow on the ground.
- II. **Green vegetation filter.** The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI, calculated from band 4 (B4) and 8 (B8) as follows $(B8-B4)/(B8+B4)$) was computed and pixels with $NDVI > 0.35$ were filtered out because they were likely affected by green vegetation.
- III. **Dry vegetation + soil moisture filter.** Normalized Burn Ratio 2 (NBR2) index was computed and pixels having $NBR2 > 0.125$ (Castaldi et al. 2019b) were filtered out because they were likely affected by dry vegetation and/or by high soil moisture content.

In the second step, if at least 3 bare soil dates were left after applying the filters for each pixel, the available data were combined to implement a mosaicking approach selecting the median (50th percentile) reflectance values for each band and pixel throughout the time series, with the aim to obtain spectral data representative of the average bare soil conditions not affected by extreme reflectance values.

The outcome of the mosaicking approach is a composite bare soil layer of 20 m resolution for each test site. Pixels close to the field borders (20 m buffer) were removed to avoid including area mixed pixels affected by spectral information of other material than soil. The layers include reflectance information of the following bands of the MSI instrument (central wavelength): B1: (443 nm), B2 (492 nm), B3 (559 nm), B4 (664 nm), B5 (704 nm), B6 (740 nm), B7 (782 nm), B8 (842 nm), B8A (865 nm), B11 (1613 nm), and B12 (2202 nm) (ESA, 2015).

4.1.3 Soil sampling strategies

4.1.3.1 Satellite-based sampling strategy

The composite bare soil layer obtained by Sentinel-2 time series was used to extract spectra from the bare soil pixels (20 m) within the boundaries of the test sites. After that the Kennard-Stone algorithm was used to

select 50 spectra corresponding to 50 pixels within the test site using the *prospectr* package (Stevens & Ramirez-Lopez, 2024) in R. The Kennard-Stone algorithm optimizes the coverage of the spectral variability, selecting spectra uniformly distributed over the feature space from the entire spectral (Castaldi, Chabrilat, & van Wesemael, 2019; Kennard & Stone, 1969). The algorithm starts finding and selecting the two spectra that are furthest apart based on the Mahalanobis distance and removing them from the input matrix. Then, the procedure was repeated until the algorithm selected the desired number of spectra that correspond to 50 pixels and therefore 50 sampling locations for the field-scale application in Italy and 20 pixels for the farm-scale experiment in Asse, Belgium.

For the Italian site, we compared the satellite-based strategy and the Random selection, obtained randomly selecting 50 points within the test site in the QGIS environment.

A composite bare soil layer was obtained both for the Italian (*Figure 17*) and the Belgian site (*Figure 18*).

Figure 17: Composite bare soil layer obtained at the Italian test site in Parma using multi-temporal Sentinel-2 collection (R: Sentinel-2 B4; G: Sentinel-2 B3; B: Sentinel-2 B2) and location of the sampling points according to the random and satellite-based sampling strategy.

Figure 18: Composite bare soil layer obtained at the Belgian test site in Asse using multi-temporal Sentinel-2 collection (R: Sentinel-2 B4; G: Sentinel-2 B3; B: Sentinel-2 B2) and location of the sampling points according to the map-based and satellite-based sampling strategy.

4.1.3.2 Map-based sampling strategy

This sampling strategy used the original PyCaret version of the original ENVISION SOC map as a source of ancillary information for the spatial variability of topsoil SOC content (see **Text box 1**). At the time of sampling (February-March 2024) the newer ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map had not yet become available. The later calibration stages of our study (see Section 4.1.5) did make use of the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map, because of its more realistic regional range in topsoil SOC content. The strategy was implemented in the freely

available and relatively user-friendly QGIS software. One of the main objectives during the development was to keep the procedure for the selection of sampling points as easily reproducible as possible for other farms throughout Flanders. The seven broad steps to this procedure are:

- 1) Division of the regional ENVISION PyCaret SOC map into ten even SOC content classes, each with a 0.1% range, between its approximate minimum (0.9%) and maximum (1.9%). To make computational power less of a limiting factor, this polygenization (i.e. change from raster layer with continuous output, to a vector layer consisting of discrete polygons) step was only done for a clipped (22 km x 16 km) portion of the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map immediately surrounding the farms (*Figure 19*). Most of the croplands surrounding the farms are characterized by, for Flanders, relatively low SOC contents, especially in the more silt-rich southern sections (see *Figure 14*) of this area.

Figure 19: Clipped and polygenized section of the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map in the immediate surroundings of the farms in Asse and Meise. The experimental field boundaries are displayed in red. The polygenization divided the continuous ENVISION PyCaret SOC map into ten even classes, each of 0.10% range between 0.9% and 1.9% SOC content.

- 2) Clipping new SOC class vector layer on field boundaries (*Figure 20*). A buffer zone of 10 m within the field boundaries was additionally clipped from the SOC class layer to minimize the impact of boundary effects, such as the shadows of trees, hedges, houses, etc..

- 3) The smallest polygons ($\leq 150 \text{ m}^2$) were excluded from the SOC class layer to enhance the chances of selecting sampling points in larger, homogeneous sections of the field, where we expect the uncertainty of the SOC map to be lower.

Figure 20: SOC classes found within the field boundaries + 10 m buffer of the farm in Asse.

- 4) To compile the farm-scale (linear) calibration dataset a pre-described number of polygons is randomly selected per SOC class (yellow frame – *Figure 21*). Five polygons were randomly selected for each of the six SOC classes present within field boundaries of the farm in Asse. However, since not all SOC classes have five polygons within the experimental boundaries, we ended up with 24 selected polygons in total: four for SOC class 1 and 4, five for 2, 3 and 5 and one for 6.
- 5) A similar procedure was followed to compile a separate field-scale validation dataset for field 1 of the farm in Asse (pink frame – *Figure 21*). This field was selected because it has the largest area (18.3 ha), while it also contains a large range of SOC classes (2-5). In total 20 additional polygons were selected: six of SOC classes 2, 3 and 4 and two of 5.

Figure 21: polygons randomly selected per SOC class for farm-scale calibration (yellow frame – $n = 24$) and field-scale validation (pink frame – $n = 20$) at the farm in Asse.

- 6) A 4 m buffer zone inside the boundaries of the selected polygons was removed to try to keep the entire sampling plots (i.e. circle of 5 m radius around the selected sampling points) within the same polygon.
- 7) Random selection of one sampling point for each buffered polygon that was selected for both calibration (step 4) and validation (step 5) (red dots – Figure 22).

Figure 22: sampling points (red dot) randomly selected within each highlighted polygon at the farm in Asse.

The same selection procedure for sampling points was applied to the farm in Meise. Because of the smaller acreage of cropland (16.2 ha) for Danial Lemmens' farm compared to the farm in Asse (71.4 ha), we decided to also limit the sample size for the local calibration dataset to twelve: three sampling points in SOC classes 2 and 4 and two in 3, 5 and 6. The field-scale validation dataset was compiled for field 2 (i.e. largest field, with relatively large range of SOC classes). To achieve an accurate estimation of the field-scale SOC content as possible, we decided to select 20 sampling points within the validation field: four for SOC classes 2 and 3, five for 4 and 5 and two for six. *Figure 23* presents the selected polygons for calibration and validation of fields 2 (validation field) and 5 in the municipality of Meise. The polygons for calibration that were selected on other fields are not included on *Figure 23* because of the large distance between the fields.

Experimental sampling campaigns for both farms concerned were performed between February 19th and 24th by ILVO field technicians.

Figure 23: sampling point (red dot) selected in fields 2 and 5 of the farm in Meise for farm-scale calibration (yellow frame - $n = 12$) and field-scale validation (pink frame - $n = 20$).

4.1.3.3 Statistical comparison between sampling strategies

The sampling strategies tested both at field- and farm-scale were compared by observing the main descriptive statistics of the SOC values and evaluating if significant differences exist in terms of variance, both for topsoil SOC content and each extracted Sentinel-2 band. The variance differences were evaluated running the Levene's test after the Box-Cox transformation to comply with the normal assumption. Only for the random sampling strategy at the field experiment in Italy, the sampling selection was repeated 100 times to obtain more robust statistics for SOC content and spectral comparison.

4.1.4 Sampling, processing and analysis protocol

4.1.4.1 Sampling

For the Belgian test sites, once on the field (*Figure 24*), the sampling point's location was identified by a CHC Navigation i90 RTK GPS (centimeter accurate). Afterwards an area with a radius of 5 m around the sampling point was marked by red sticks, within which 8 subsamples were collected randomly from two separate

topsoil intervals (0-10 cm & 10-30 cm) by means of an auger with a diameter of 2.5 cm. The subsamples were thoroughly mixed and stored in a labelled plastic bag for transportation to the laboratory. The same procedure was adopted for the Italian site, except that the subsamples were collected without separating two topsoil intervals. In Italy, we collected 50 soil samples according to the random approach and 50 according to the satellite-based approach, however, 6 samples (3 for each sampling strategy) have been lost.

Figure 24: Sampling protocol per plot (5m radius) with 8 randomly distributed sub-sampling points

4.1.4.2 Processing samples

For the soil samples collected in the Belgian test site, visual plant material that is larger than 2 mm was removed from the moist sample. The soil was dried for at least 24h at 40 +/-2°C. The sample was grounded with a jaw crusher (crushers at 1.5 mm) and sieved at 2 mm. Material that did not pass the sieve was crushed manually in a mortar and again sieved at 2 mm. As a final step, the sample was further milled with a Fritsch Pulverisette 6, Planetary Mill to < 250 µm. The soil samples collected in Italy were processed in the same way as in Belgium, except for the mechanical crushing, which was left out of the process.

4.1.4.3 Analysis samples

Soil total carbon content for Italian and Belgian site was measured by dry combustion at 1100 °C using a Skalar C/N-Analyzer Primacs SNC100-IC (ISO 10694:1995). The inorganic carbon content was measured after acid addition using a Skalar C/N-Analyzer Primacs SNC100-IC (NBN EN 15936), but only if the pH-KCl of the sample is above 6.5. The SOC data was the result of total carbon content minus the inorganic carbon content of the

sample. Results are expressed as % on absolute dry matter (residual moisture correction, measured by drying at 105°C).

4.1.5 Local (farm-scale) calibration of regional SOC map

Linear regression analysis was used to determine the local (farm-scale) relationships (calibration line – ijklijn) between the SOC estimates of the original (regional) ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map and the measured SOC content at the sample points. This analysis was repeated several times with an increasing number of sample points being taken up into the calibration dataset. For the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Asse six sample sizes were included in the analysis: 3, 6, 11, 16, 21 and 24. For the satellite-based sampling strategy at the farm in Asse four sample sizes were included: 3, 6, 12 and 20. At the farm in Meise four sample sizes (only map-based sampling strategy) were included: 3, 5, 10 en 12. The inclusion of the sample point selected with the map-based sampling strategy into the calibration dataset depended on the corresponding SOC class (see Section 4.1.3.2) of the point. The first sample size included one sample point from each of the two extreme (lowest and highest) SOC classes found within the farm and one from middle SOC class. The second sample size included one sample point from each of the remaining SOC classes. The following sample sizes were compiled by randomly adding one sampling point per remaining SOC class. In this way, a specified order was maintained based on the SOC classes, but within the SOC classes the selection of the sample points was completely random and could thus be repeated six times per sample size (except for the highest sample size) to obtain a measure for the uncertainty of the local calibration process. With the sample points selected with the satellite-based sampling strategy the order was completely fixed by the Kennard-Stone algorithm and so no value could be calculated for the uncertainty. Afterwards, the original ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map was adapted according to the local calibration lines in QGIS with the ‘Raster calculations’ tool. Further in the report, the calibrated SOC maps will be referred to by the farm and the sample size used for the regression analysis.

Validation of the locally calibrated SOC maps was performed with independent datasets compiled with 20 sampling points at one selected field per farm. For the farm in Asse this was field 1 and for the farm in Meise this was field 2 (see Section 4.1.3.2). We looked at the R^2 , as a value for the random error of the prediction model, the root mean squared error (RMSE), as a value for the total error, the mean error (ME), as a value for the systematic error or bias, and the ratio of performance to deviation (RPD), as a value for the overall quality of the prediction model.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Spectral comparison

4.2.1.1 Field experiment

The average spectrum of the 47 satellite-based and 47 random sampling points looks very similar to each other (*Figure 25*) and to the average of the whole spectral dataset composed of 150 bare soil spectra extracted from the 150 pixels of the composite bare soil layer. No significant differences were found for all the average values of the Sentinel-2 bands. No significant difference exists either between satellite-based and random bands in terms of variance based on Levene's test and neither between satellite-based spectra and whole dataset. Therefore, it seems that both satellite-based and random approach selected the same variability for each band of the entire spectral population.

Figure 25: Average bare soil spectrum extracted in correspondence of the random (green line) and satellite-based (blue) sampling points at the Italian test site in Parma.

Significant differences in terms of variance between random and Satellite-based can be more often observed for B2, and B12 where the Satellite-based generally showed a higher variance and for B3, B4 and B11 where is random selection which instead has a higher variance; the other bands showed similar variances comparing the two sampling approaches. Only B5, B6 and B8A showed a clear reduction in the frequency of significant

differences between the two sampling approaches increasing the sampling size, in this case satellite-based strategy normally has a higher variance for B6 and B8A, while for B5 random selection provided higher variance.

4.2.1.2 Farm experiment

The average spectrum of the 20 satellite-based and 20 map-based spectra are similar in shape and reflectance value for each band (Figure 26). No significant differences were found between the two average spectra, neither in terms of variance based on Levene's test. Therefore, the satellite-based approach selected, without *a priori* information about the SOC distribution, the same spectral variability as the map-based approach.

Figure 26: Average bare soil spectrum extracted in correspondence of the satellite-based (blue line) and map-based (orange line) sampling points at the Belgian test site in Asse.

4.2.2 SOC content comparison

4.2.2.1 Field test site

We compared the SOC content statistics between the random and satellite-based approach for different sampling sizes, from 10 to 47 samples. For the random approach the selection was repeated 100 times, and the average values were extracted for the comparison.

The SOC content range increases according to the number of soil samples both for the random and satellite-based approach (*Figure 27*). The SOC content ranges obtained by the random selection are wider than those derived by the satellite-based approach until 35 samples, after that, the SOC content range becomes larger for the satellite-based method; this is due to the sharp increase of the maximum SOC content values for the satellite-based approach after selecting 36 samples. At this point the two curves of the maximum values come very close and will continue with parallel trend. The minimum SOC content values remain lower for the satellite-based approach as compared to randomly selected samples. Therefore, the satellite-based approach did not markedly increase the SOC content range for sampling size lower than 35, but it is more efficient for selecting the left side of the SOC content distribution. In fact, both the mean and median values observed for the satellite-based samples are generally lower as compared to random approach, which generally showed a left-skewed distribution (*Table 7*).

Figure 27: Minimum, maximum and range of SOC content (%) for random and satellite-based sampling strategies according to the number of samples

Table 7: Topsoil SOC content (% - 0-10cm) distribution, determined from the satellite-based and random sampling strategy at the Italian test site with increasing sample size (n)

Sample size (n) ^o	Satellite-based						Random					
	Min	Max	Mean	Median	Std	Skewness	Min	Max	Mean	Median	Std	Skewness
10	1.01	1.84	1.39	1.38	0.29	0.22	1.34	3.12	2.28	2.35	0.58	-0.19
11	1.01	1.84	1.42	1.46	0.29	0.04	1.34	3.13	2.28	2.34	0.56	-0.19
12	1.01	1.95	1.46	1.49	0.32	0.04	1.31	3.20	2.31	2.38	0.58	-0.22
13	1.01	1.95	1.44	1.46	0.32	0.17	1.28	3.23	2.29	2.36	0.58	-0.20
14	1.01	1.95	1.44	1.44	0.30	0.19	1.28	3.30	2.30	2.36	0.58	-0.12
15	1.01	1.95	1.43	1.42	0.30	0.27	1.22	3.26	2.27	2.35	0.59	-0.19
16	1.01	2.53	1.50	1.44	0.40	0.95	1.21	3.28	2.30	2.38	0.58	-0.24
17	1.01	2.53	1.49	1.42	0.39	1.04	1.19	3.38	2.29	2.34	0.59	-0.12
18	1.01	2.53	1.49	1.44	0.37	1.03	1.21	3.34	2.30	2.39	0.58	-0.19
19	1.01	2.53	1.49	1.46	0.36	1.05	1.17	3.41	2.29	2.38	0.60	-0.14
20	1.01	2.53	1.49	1.46	0.35	1.10	1.12	3.36	2.27	2.35	0.59	-0.22
21	0.88	2.53	1.46	1.45	0.37	0.93	1.14	3.41	2.27	2.35	0.59	-0.13
22	0.88	2.53	1.44	1.43	0.38	0.91	1.14	3.35	2.28	2.37	0.58	-0.22
23	0.88	2.53	1.44	1.45	0.37	0.91	1.13	3.45	2.28	2.36	0.59	-0.14
24	0.88	2.53	1.44	1.46	0.36	0.91	1.13	3.42	2.28	2.36	0.58	-0.15
25	0.51	2.53	1.41	1.45	0.40	0.40	1.11	3.46	2.29	2.37	0.58	-0.17
26	0.51	2.53	1.39	1.43	0.40	0.44	1.12	3.47	2.29	2.38	0.58	-0.18
27	0.51	2.53	1.38	1.42	0.40	0.50	1.09	3.49	2.28	2.36	0.59	-0.16
28	0.51	2.53	1.38	1.39	0.39	0.51	1.08	3.52	2.28	2.37	0.59	-0.14
29	0.51	2.53	1.36	1.36	0.40	0.47	1.08	3.53	2.29	2.38	0.59	-0.16
30	0.51	2.53	1.34	1.35	0.41	0.41	1.07	3.54	2.29	2.38	0.58	-0.16
31	0.51	2.53	1.33	1.35	0.41	0.46	1.05	3.53	2.28	2.37	0.59	-0.17
32	0.51	2.53	1.30	1.33	0.42	0.40	1.07	3.56	2.29	2.37	0.59	-0.14
33	0.51	2.53	1.31	1.35	0.42	0.37	1.05	3.54	2.28	2.37	0.59	-0.18
34	0.51	2.53	1.34	1.35	0.45	0.48	1.05	3.59	2.29	2.38	0.59	-0.16
35	0.51	3.34	1.40	1.36	0.56	1.26	1.03	3.57	2.29	2.38	0.59	-0.19
36	0.51	3.34	1.39	1.35	0.55	1.30	1.03	3.61	2.29	2.37	0.59	-0.14
37	0.51	3.34	1.39	1.36	0.55	1.32	1.03	3.58	2.29	2.37	0.58	-0.18
38	0.51	3.34	1.41	1.38	0.55	1.21	1.02	3.62	2.29	2.37	0.59	-0.14
39	0.51	3.34	1.41	1.40	0.54	1.23	1.02	3.63	2.29	2.39	0.59	-0.16
40	0.51	3.34	1.42	1.40	0.54	1.18	1.00	3.63	2.28	2.36	0.59	-0.15
41	0.51	3.34	1.46	1.41	0.59	1.18	1.00	3.66	2.28	2.36	0.59	-0.13
42	0.51	3.34	1.49	1.41	0.62	1.09	1.00	3.63	2.29	2.37	0.59	-0.17
43	0.51	3.52	1.54	1.42	0.68	1.19	0.99	3.63	2.29	2.37	0.59	-0.18
44	0.51	3.52	1.57	1.43	0.72	1.12	0.99	3.67	2.29	2.38	0.59	-0.17
45	0.51	3.52	1.59	1.45	0.72	1.07	0.98	3.67	2.29	2.37	0.59	-0.16
46	0.51	3.52	1.59	1.46	0.71	1.06	0.98	3.68	2.29	2.37	0.59	-0.16
47	0.51	3.52	1.62	1.46	0.74	0.99	0.98	3.69	2.29	2.38	0.59	-0.16

The variance trends according to the sampling size is quite different between the random and satellite-based sampling strategies: an almost constant trend for random, while for the satellite-based approach we observed a first sharp increase after 35 samples and a second after 40 (Figure 28). The variance of the random approach is higher than the satellite-based approach until 42 samples, after that the satellite-based approach was able to catch more SOC content variability. The Levene's test for the equality of the variances provided most of the times significant differences between the tested approaches, except using 35-40 samples.

Figure 28: Variance of the SOC content (%) for random and satellite-based sampling strategies according to the number of samples

4.2.2.2 Farm test sites

The results for SOC content from the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Asse are presented per SOC class (i.e. strata) in Table 8. The measured SOC content has a markedly higher range (0.71-2.47%) than the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map predicted (0.90-1.50%), but the general order of the SOC classes is still followed. This is especially true for the extreme values: the four lowest SOC contents are all found in SOC class 1 and the highest value is found in SOC class 6 and the second highest in SOC class 5. In the middle SOC classes (2-5) the differences become less discernable. The variability (CV) within several SOC classes comes very close to the total farm-scale variability (26.2%). Only SOC classes 1 (9.0%) and 3 (15.8%) and show a clear difference with the overall variability. This sampling strategy thus seems to be effective at covering the entire range of farm-scale SOC content, even at relatively low sampling sizes, but is less effective at limiting the variability within the SOC classes or strata (compared to the total variability), which would be required to help reduce the sample size compared to more simple random or geographical sampling strategies (Bettigole et al., 2023; De Gruijter et al., 2006; Peltoniemi et al., 2007). There appear to be environmental or management factors at play that could explain a sizeable portion of the SOC content spatial variability which is not covered by

differences in the soil's spectral patterns. The map-based sampling strategy might therefore win in cost-efficiency by adding new sources of ancillary data. However, it could also be that the range of the ENVISION PyCaret SOC estimates per SOC class was simply too small compared to the prediction models accuracy. It might have been more prudent to select an intra SOC class range that was higher than the RMSE of the ENVISION PyCaret prediction model for the Soil Association region of the farm in Asse (see *Figure 3 - #32*: 0.19%).

Table 8: SOC content (% - 0-10 cm) from the map-based sampling strategy per SOC class observed on the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map at the farm in Asse (n=24)

SOC class	PyCaret SOC prediction interval (%)	SOC content (% - 0-10 cm)						
		Sample size	Avg. (%)	St. Dev. (%)	CV (%)	Min. (%)	Max. (%)	Area (m ²)
1	0.9 - 1.0	4	0.78	0.07	9.0	0.71	0.86	1452
2	1.0 - 1.1	5	1.26	0.30	23.8	0.91	1.81	214951
3	1.1 - 1.2	5	1.33	0.21	15.8	1.01	1.59	342399
4	1.2 - 1.3	4	1.30	0.28	21.5	0.98	1.68	54814
5	1.3 - 1.4	5	1.51	0.41	27.2	1.16	2.30	6046
6	1.4 - 1.5	1	2.47	-	-	-	-	524
Total	0.9 - 1.5	24	1.30*	0.34	26.2	0.71	2.47	620186

*Area adjusted for SOC classes within the farm's field boundaries

The measured SOC content is still relatively highly correlated to the ENVISION PyCaret SOC estimates. The correlation with the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC estimates could be considered rather moderate (*Table 9*). Another noteworthy result from this table is the low correlation between the two ENVISION SOC maps.

Table 9: Correlation between three different sources of SOC content determination: measured with laboratory analysis and estimates from PyCaret and TensorFlow versions of the original ENVISION SOC maps at the farm in Asse (n=24)

	SOC content (0-10 cm)	Original Pycaret	Original TensorFlow
SOC content (0-10 cm)	1.00		
PyCaret SOC prediction	0.69	1.00	
TensorFlow SOC prediction	0.51	0.32	1.00

Table 10 presents the average SOC content predictions per field of the farm in Asse determined from the samples of the map-based sampling strategy, using the average per SOC class (*Table 8*), and from the estimates of both the original (regional) ENVISION SOC maps. Both ENVISION SOC maps make a systematic underestimation of the SOC content, but this is slightly less the case for the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map. For the only field with a relatively high intra-field samples size (field 1 – n=27), the overall average of all the samples was 1.18%, so actually closer to the estimations of the original ENVISION PyCaret (1.12%) and TensorFlow (1.15%) SOC maps than the 1.32% determined at farm-scale with the map-based sampling strategy. The within-field spatial variability (CV) was relatively low for both ENVISION SOC maps compared to the results from the literature studies discussed in *Table 1*. At farm-scale the spatial variability for these SOC

maps remained just as low, much lower than the value determined for the map-based sampling strategy (26.2%).

Table 10: Area-adjusted (for SOC classes) average SOC content (%) determined by laboratory analysis and average (%), standard deviation (%) and CV (%) of the SOC content derived from the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map and ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map for each field of the farm in Asse.

Field nr.	Area (ha)	SOC content Avg. (%)	Original PyCaret			Original TensorFlow		
			Avg. (%)	St. Dev. (%)	CV (%)	Avg. (%)	St. Dev. (%)	CV (%)
1	18.3	1.32	1.12	0.06	5.4	1.15	0.05	4.3
2	7.2	1.31	1.07	0.03	2.8	1.13	0.02	1.8
3	2.9	1.29	1.10	0.03	2.7	1.18	0.04	3.4
4	1.1	1.30	1.10	0.03	2.7	1.17	0.04	3.4
5	4.6	1.29	1.15	0.06	5.2	1.12	0.02	1.8
6	2.0	1.31	1.13	0.04	3.5	1.26	0.10	7.9
7	0.4	1.40	1.16	0.05	4.3	1.22	0.03	2.5
8	0.7	1.31	1.15	0.03	2.6	1.27	0.07	5.5
9	0.9	1.32	1.11	0.03	2.7	1.19	0.03	2.5
10	1.8	1.32	1.08	0.06	5.6	1.18	0.05	4.2
11	3.9	1.26	1.06	0.04	3.8	1.07	0.01	0.9
12	2.1	1.31	1.11	0.03	2.7	1.14	0.02	1.8
13	1.0	1.27	1.10	0.04	3.6	1.14	0.02	1.8
14	4.6	1.33	1.29	0.06	4.7	1.16	0.03	2.6
15	5.5	1.28	1.14	0.04	3.5	1.15	0.03	2.6
16	2.4	1.29	1.12	0.04	3.6	1.19	0.04	3.4
17	3.7	1.32	1.13	0.04	3.5	1.09	0.03	2.8
18	8.0	1.29	1.13	0.06	5.3	1.13	0.02	1.8
19	0.4	1.32	1.11	0.04	3.6	1.12	0.03	2.7
Total	71.4	1.30	1.13	0.04	3.5	1.14	0.01	0.9

In Figure 29, the results for minimum, maximum and range of the measured SOC content from the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Asse are compared with the corresponding results from the satellite-based sampling strategy. For the minimum value there is a clear congruence between both sampling strategies, but this is not the case for the maximum value, and therefore also range. Just as was noticed in Figure 27 at field-scale in Italy, the satellite-based sampling strategy proved to be more efficient at selecting the left side of the SOC content distribution than the right side. However, this difference between the sampling strategies might also be explained by the extended buffer zone of 20 m for satellite-based compared to 10 m for map-based. It is in this diverging zone that most of the polygons for SOC classes 5 and 6 could be found, and so also almost all high SOC contents. The zone of between 10 m and 20 m from the field border often falls within the field's headland, where traffic intensity is highest and most turning is done (Augustin et al., 2020), both contributing to a higher risk of soil compaction (Sunoj et al., 2021; Welch et al., 2016). Despite its lower crop yields (e.g. Sunoj et al., 2021), and thus lower potential carbon inputs, the headlands have been previously shown to have relatively high levels of SOC (e.g. Welch et al., 2016), which could be explained by the reduced carbon mineralization under higher bulk densities, observed by De Neve & Hofman (2000) for loamy sand soils, that

would allow for carbon accumulation over time (Welch et al., 2016). It is striking how little the lines for both sampling strategies change across the tested sample sizes. This seems to highlight the ability of the sampling strategies to efficiently pick SOC extremes with their respective zone of interest.

Figure 29: Minimum, maximum and range of SOC content (%) for the map- and satellite-based sampling strategies at the farm in Asse according to the sample size

The variance trends according to the sampling size are remarkably different between the map- and satellite-based sampling strategies for the farm in Asse: an almost constant trend for the satellite-based approach with relatively low variance (~0.06%), while the map-based approach started with very high variance (0.50%), which decreased exponentially with the sample size to more steady state around 0.20% (Figure 30). Levene’s test did, however, not show any significant differences in variance between map- and satellite-based sampling strategies qua SOC content. This can probably be explained by the fact that much of the high variance of the map-based approach is caused by a limited number of samples with really high SOC content.

Figure 30 also presents the trend of the variance according to the sample size for the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Meise. At this farm the map-based approach does not show an exponential decline in variance with the sample size. The SOC variance makes an initial steep rise from sample size 3 to 6 and then starts to decline steadily but does not reach a steady state within the rather limited range of tested sample sizes.

Figure 30: Variance of the SOC content (%) for the map- and satellite-based sampling strategies at the farm in Asse and the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Meise, all according to the sample size

The results for SOC content from the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Meise are presented per SOC class in *Table 11*. Just as for the farm in Asse (*Table 8*), the SOC content has a markedly higher range (1.17-3.23%) than the ENVISION Pycaret SOC map predicted (1.00-1.50%). However, here the general order of the SOC classes is not really followed. The lowest SOC contents were found in the lowest (2) and highest (6) SOC classes, while the highest SOC contents were in the middle SOC classes (3-5). The intra SOC class variability for all classes, except for 2, is notably lower than the overall farm-scale variability. Although, we need to consider here the low number of samples per SOC class. The higher number of Soil Association regions that are found within the farm in Meise (*Table 6*) compared to the farm in Asse (*Table 5*) is represented by the higher farm-scale standard deviation in SOC content (0.57% vs. 0.34%), but the markedly higher measured SOC contents for the farm in Meise did result in similar CV values for both farms (28.5% vs. 26.2%).

Table 11: SOC content (% - 0-10 cm) from the map-based sampling strategy per SOC class observed on the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map at the farm in Meise (n=12)

SOC class	PyCaret SOC prediction interval (%)	SOC content (% - 0-10 cm)						
		Sample size	Avg. (%)	St. Dev. (%)	CV (%)	Min. (%)	Max. (%)	Area (m ²)
1	0.9 - 1.0	0	-	-	-	-	-	0
2	1.0 - 1.1	3	1.46	0.38	26.0	1.17	1.99	32621
3	1.1 - 1.2	2	2.42	0.06	2.5	2.36	2.48	61346
4	1.2 - 1.3	3	2.10	0.06	2.9	2.06	2.19	26153
5	1.3 - 1.4	2	2.77	0.47	17.0	2.30	3.23	12178
6	1.4 - 1.5	2	1.48	0.06	4.1	1.42	1.54	1363
Total	0.9 - 1.5	12	2.00	0.57	28.5	1.17	3.23	133661

*Area adjusted for SOC classes within the farm's field boundaries

We observed a very low correlation between the measured SOC content and the ENVISION PyCaret SOC estimates, while the correlation with the ENVISION TensorFlow was high (*Table 12*). The ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map would probably have been a much better source of ancillary data, compared to the PyCaret version, to provide knowledge on the farm-scale spatial variability in SOC content. Similarly, as at the farm in Asse (*Table 9*), the PyCaret and TensorFlow SOC maps showed a weak correlation to each other.

Table 12: Correlation between three different sources of SOC content (% - 0-10 cm) determination: measured with laboratory analysis and estimates from PyCaret and TensorFlow versions of the original ENVISION SOC maps at the farm in Meise (n=32)

	SOC content (0-10 cm)	Original Pycaret	Original TensorFlow
SOC content (0-10 cm)	1.00		
PyCaret SOC prediction	0.09	1.00	
TensorFlow SOC prediction	0.81	-0.32	1.00

Table 13 presents the average SOC content predictions per field of the farm in Meise determined from the samples of the map-based sampling strategy, using the average per SOC class (*Table 11*), and from the estimates of both the original (regional) ENVISION SOC maps. Both ENVISION SOC maps make a markedly high systematic underestimation of the SOC content. However, whereas the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map estimates the field-scale SOC content at both Belgian test sites to be of a similar order of magnitude (*Table 10*), the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map did estimate relatively high field-scale SOC contents for some of the fields of the farm in Meise (fields 6, 7 and 8). This difference in Soil Association regions (*Table 6*) does seem to be better visible in the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map. For the only field with a relatively high intra-field samples size (field 2 – n=22), the overall average of all the samples was 2.11%, so the determination at farm-scale with the map-based sampling strategy (2.26% – n=12) is much more exact than the ENVISION SOC maps (PyCaret: 1.19%; TensorFlow: 1.19%), but it still does not have the accuracy we would expect for carbon farming initiatives (Andries et al., 2021). As expected from the geographical and feature space spread of the fields, the within-field variability at the farm in Meise was slightly higher than at the more spatially concentrated farm in Asse. However, the values were still lower than would be expected by the results discussed in *Table 1*. The ENVISION PyCaret SOC map predicted a farm-scale variability that was of a similar magnitude than the field-scale variability, much lower than the value determined for the map-based sampling strategy (28.5%). In contrast, the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map predicted an approximately twice as high farm-scale variability compared to the field-scale. Goidts et al. (2009) did not observe large increases in spatial variability of SOC stocks from field- to landscape-scale for croplands in Wallonia, Belgium. But Saby et al. (2008) did observe a steady increase in spatial variability of SOC content with increasing spatial scales in a review of European field studies.

Table 13: Area-adjusted (for SOC classes) average SOC content (%) determined by laboratory analysis and average (%), standard deviation (%) and CV (%) of the SOC content derived from the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map and ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map for each field of the farm in Meise.

Field nr.	Area (ha)	SOC content	Original Pycaret			Original TensorFlow		
		Avg. (%)	Avg. (%)	St. Dev. (%)	CV (%)	Avg. (%)	St. Dev. (%)	CV (%)
1	0.4	1.82	1.08	0.03	2.8	1.14	0.06	5.3
2	4.1	2.26	1.19	0.07	5.9	1.19	0.07	5.9
3	0.8	1.96	1.10	0.04	3.6	1.09	0.02	1.8
4	0.9	1.88	1.12	0.05	4.5	1.15	0.04	3.5
5	2.3	2.34	1.24	0.10	8.1	1.15	0.05	4.3
6	2.4	1.86	1.09	0.04	3.7	1.15	0.02	1.7
7	1.0	1.80	1.16	0.12	10.3	1.40	0.06	4.2
8	3.0	2.19	1.17	0.08	6.8	1.44	0.05	3.5
9	1.4	2.29	1.19	0.10	8.4	1.46	0.05	3.4
Total	16.3	2.14	1.17	0.09	7.7	1.25	0.14	11.2

In *Figure 31* the different SOC contents determined by soil sampling and laboratory analysis and estimated by the original (regional) ENVISION PyCaret and TensorFlow SOC maps are presented per soil type at the two Belgian test sites (*Table 5* *Table 6*). While soil type had a significant impact ($P < 0.01$) on the measured SOC content, its impact on the estimates of the ENVISION SOC maps was much more limited. The mean measured SOC content for the silt soils (1.18%) was well estimated by the ENVISION PyCaret (1.15%) and TensorFlow (1.14%) SOC maps, but not for the sandy loam soils, where the mean measured SOC content (2.08%) was markedly underestimated by the ENVISION PyCaret (1.23%) and TensorFlow (1.21%) SOC maps. The measured SOC content was also characterized by high variation for both silt (standard deviation: 0.35%) and sandy loam (0.43%) soils, which was not translated by the ENVISION (silt: 0.10%; sandy loam: 0.12%) and TensorFlow (silt: 0.07%; sandy loam: 0.12%) SOC maps. It seems likely that the ENVISION prediction models could be greatly improved by adding data points from distinct soil types in Flanders to the calibration dataset. However, since our results are collected from just two farms, it could also be that differences in management practices play an important role in the differences observed in *Figure 31*.

Figure 31: SOC content (% - 0-10 cm) at the two Belgian test sites, determined by soil sampling and laboratory analysis (blue) and predicted by the original ENVISION PyCaret (orange) and TensorFlow (green) SOC maps per soil type of the Belgian soil classification

A similar story was observed for the drainage classes at the two Belgian test sites (Figure 32). Both ENVISION SOC maps had more difficulty predicting slower draining soils. While the ENVISION SOC maps made a slight overestimation of the “dry” soils, the “moist” and “wet” soils were considerably underestimated. Soil moisture disturbs the spectral signal of the SWIR bands and thereby negatively influences the estimation of SOC content (Castaldi, Chabrilat, Don, et al., 2019; Nocita et al., 2013). Inclusion of ancillary data on soil moisture content (or drainage class), like soil moisture maps that could be derived from Sentinel-1 and -2 spectral data (e.g. Bazzi et al., 2024; El Hajj et al., 2017; Vaudour et al., 2022), could help to increase the accuracy of remote sensing SOC content estimation methods.

Figure 32: SOC content (% - 0-10 cm) at the two Belgian test sites, determined by soil sampling and laboratory analysis (blue) and predicted by the original ENVISION PyCaret (orange) and TensorFlow (green) SOC maps per drainage class of the Belgian soil classification

4.2.3 Local calibration

Figure 33 presents the relationships (calibration lines) between the estimates of the original (regional) ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map and the results from the map- and satellite-based sampling strategies at the farm in Asse and the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Meise at different sample sizes. Almost all local calibration lines had a steeper slope than the ideal (1:1) calibration line, which highlights the much lower range of the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map than the SOC content measurements at both Belgian test sites (Table 8 Table 11). For the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Asse, the slope of the calibration lines gradually decreased with increasing sample size. For the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Meise, the slope of the calibration lines remained roughly constant with increasing sample size. At lower sample sizes ($n < 10$), there was substantial uncertainty (i.e. variation between replication calibration lines) for the local calibration lines from the map-based sampling strategies. The map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Asse started with a high correlation at a sample size of 3, but with increasing sample size the correlation fell back considerably. For the satellite-based sampling strategy at the farm in Asse, the opposite was true: it started with a low correlation at a sample size of 3, but with the addition of 3 extra sample points (and more) the correlation was doubled. The map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Meise resulted in a similar situation, although with a less striking increase in correlation for the increase in sample size from 3 to 5. At the farm in Meise, the local calibration lines indicated a systematic underestimation of the SOC content within

the local range of the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map (1.0-1.5%). At the farm in Asse the calibration lines of both sampling strategies indicated an overestimation of the low SOC contents and underestimation of the high SOC contents.

Figure 33: Local (farm-scale) calibration lines created with increasing sample sizes (n) from the map- and satellite-based calibration datasets for the farm in Asse and the map-based calibration dataset for the farm in Meise

The validation of the original (regional) ENVISION PyCaret and TensorFlow SOC maps and the locally (farm-scale) calibrated, with different sample sizes, ENVISION TensorFlow SOC maps was performed at field-scale (Asse: field 1; Meise: field 2). The results from the map- and satellite-based sampling strategies at the farm in Asse are presented in *Table 14* *Table 15*, respectively. The results from the map-based sampling strategy at the farm in Meise are presented in *Table 16*.

The original ENVISION PyCaret and TensorFlow SOC estimates at field 2 of the farm in Asse (*Table 14*) were characterized by an accuracy (RMSE) that was slightly lower than at regional-scale (#32; see Figure 3), almost no bias (ME) and an unreliable quality of the prediction model (RPD). There was a large difference in the random error (R^2), which was very low for the ENVISION PyCaret SOC map and relatively high for the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map. The local calibration of the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map decreased the accuracy at lower sample sizes, but slightly increased it at higher sample sizes ($n \geq 11$). The accuracy at higher sample sizes fell within the range of the minimum detectable change (0.05-0.21%) that was observed by Deluz et al. (2020) for their farm-scale sampling strategy in Switzerland. The local calibration resulted in an increase in bias. The validation points were systematically overestimated. The bias did decrease with increasing sample sizes, but remained steady from sample size 11 onward. The RPD was drastically reduced by local calibration at lower sample sizes, but then gradually increased at higher sample sizes. At a sample size of 16 the prediction model could be considered fair (Chang et al., 2001).

Table 14: Field-scale validation parameters for the original (regional) ENVISION PyCaret and TensorFlow SOC maps and the locally (farm-scale – Asse) calibrated ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map with increasing sample size (n) that were collected according to the map-based sampling strategy.

Validation parameters	Original PyCaret	Original TensorFlow	Locally calibrated TensorFlow					
			n=3	n=6	n=11	n=16	n=21	n=24
RMSE	0.23	0.20	0.52	0.29	0.20	0.17	0.16	0.18
ME	0.03	-0.01	0.37	0.19	0.12	0.09	0.09	0.09
R^2	0.07	0.73	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.53
RPD	1.02	1.19	0.51	0.86	1.21	1.43	1.45	1.27

Using the dataset from the satellite-based sampling strategy at the farm in Asse to calibrate the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map did not result in notable changes in accuracy or quality of the prediction model, which remained quite unreliable (*Table 15*). The random error was slightly reduced, even at very low sample sizes, while the bias was increased. The validation points were systematically underestimated.

Table 15: Field-scale validation parameters for the original (regional) ENVISION PyCaret and TensorFlow SOC maps and the locally (farm-scale – Asse) calibrated ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map with increasing sample size (n) that were collected according to the satellite-based sampling strategy.

Validation parameters	Original PyCaret	Original TensorFlow	Locally calibrated TensorFlow			
			n=3	n=6	n=12	n=20
RMSE	0.23	0.20	0.22	0.19	0.19	0.20
ME	0.03	-0.01	-0.10	-0.12	-0.11	-0.10

R²	0.07	0.73	0.76	0.76	0.78	0.76
RPD	1.02	1.19	1.05	1.22	1.22	1.19

The original ENVISION PyCaret and TensorFlow SOC estimates at field 2 of the farm in Meise (*Table 16*) were characterized by a very low accuracy, much lower than at regional scale (#29 – RMSE = 0.03; see Figure 3), a very high bias and an unreliable quality of the prediction model. There was a large difference in the random error, but it was very high for both ENVISION SOC maps. The local calibration of the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map decreased the accuracy by approximately 50%, but the sample size had no effect on this improvement. However, the accuracy remained far too low to allow the calibrated SOC map to be used for carbon farming initiatives (Andries et al., 2021). The local calibration also decreased the bias, but there remained a considerable underestimation of the validation points. Similar stories for the random error and quality of the prediction model: noteworthy improvement, but with a result that still falls short of thresholds for applicability (Andries et al., 2021; Piikki et al., 2021; Vaudour et al., 2022).

Table 16: Field-scale validation parameters for the original (regional) ENVISION PyCaret and TensorFlow SOC maps and the locally (farm-scale – Meise) calibrated ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map with increasing sample size (*n*) that were collected according to the map-based sampling strategy.

Validation parameters	Original PyCaret	Original TensorFlow	Locally calibrated TensorFlow			
			n=3	n=5	n=10	n=12
RMSE	0.93	0.96	0.50	0.47	0.50	0.52
ME	-0.89	-0.93	-0.45	-0.42	-0.46	-0.48
R²	0.01	0.37	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47
RPD	0.29	0.28	0.56	0.59	0.55	0.52

Research question 2 (Section 4): Can the Sentinel-2 spectral bands (satellite-based) or pre-existing SOC maps (map-based – e.g. ENVISION PyCaret SOC map for the region of Flanders) provide us with adequate knowledge on topsoil SOC variability at field- and farm-scale to help optimize soil sampling strategies?

At field-scale, the satellite-based approach increased the SOC content range for sample sizes higher than 35 (about 4 soil samples per hectare) compared to the random approach. The satellite-based strategy was more efficient for selecting the left side of the SOC content distribution, allowing detection of the lowest SOC values. For a sampling size of 42 (about 5 samples per hectare), the satellite-based approach caught a much higher SOC content variability than random sampling strategy. The differences between the two sampling approaches could be attributable to the wider variability in B12 values detected by the satellite-based approach, especially for larger sampling size. This SWIR band is indeed the one most correlated with SOC values. Therefore, the satellite-based approach proved to be adequate for planning an accurate soil sampling campaign at field-scale that covers all the SOC variability, without *a priori* information. In comparison to random selection, the satellite-based approach seems more efficient for a sampling density higher than 4 samples per hectare.

At farm-scale, from a spectral point of view, the satellite-based approach selected, without *a priori* information about the SOC distribution, the same spectral variability as the map-based approach. This map-based approach did manage to select a markedly higher, although still insignificant, portion of the SOC spatial variability than the satellite-based approach. However, this difference was presumably caused by the extended buffer zone of 20 m for satellite-based compared to 10 m for map-based, which probably excluded much of the right side of the farm-scale SOC distribution. While the map-based sampling strategy proved to be effective at covering the entire range of farm-scale SOC content, even at low sampling sizes, it was less effective at limiting the variability within the SOC classes (i.e. strata). To make this approach more viable for carbon farming or monitoring initiatives the utilized SOC map would have to be substantially improved to better consider differences in environmental factors, like soil type and soil moisture content or drainage class. The relatively small calibration dataset for the original (regional) ENVISION SOC maps would have to be expanded with extra data points, based on more detailed differences in texture and drainage classes, information that is readily available on the Belgian Soil Map. Additionally, the map-based approach would probably be improved by working with broader ranges (e.g. 0.20%) for the SOC content estimates of the SOC classes (i.e. strata).

Research question 3 (Section 4): Is it possible to meaningfully increase the accuracy of the ENVISION TensorFlow SOC map at field-scale by its local (i.e. farm-scale) calibration?

We did manage to increase the accuracy and quality of the TensorFlow SOC map at field scale by its farm-scale calibration. The map-based sampling strategy proved to be a slightly better approach to compile the farm-scale calibration dataset for this purpose. Even at small sample sizes of around 10, we observed noteworthy improvements. However, these improvements still fell short of most thresholds for applicability in carbon farming or monitoring initiatives.

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